

Physical activity of adolescents in health and recreation facilities: motives and interests

Taras Bondar
Iryna Holoviichuk

University of Customs and Finance, Dnipro, Ukraine

Purpose: elucidation of the motives and interests of adolescents regarding forms of physical activity in health and recreation facilities.

Material & Methods: in a sociological study, adolescents aged 10–15 years participated in children's health and recreation facilities.

Results: in the process of analyzing the survey data, it was found that for adolescent boys, regardless of age, in the exercise and sports, the existence of certain rules and boundaries is very important, which affects their interest and motivation. For girls, on the contrary, the existence of rules and boundaries is a factor that reduces the interest in physical exercises. The presence of emotional coloring and a variety of motor modes, on the contrary, stimulate girls' creativity and imagination, which leads to their enjoyment of motor activity.

Conclusions: in the process of analyzing the survey data, the diversity and non-standard interests of adolescents in physical education and sports and the gender characteristics of their motivation were established. The identified need for the development of organizational and managerial technologies that will take into account the interests and motives of adolescents, with the aim of their active involvement in motor activity.

Keywords: physical education, permission, health care, motivation, tourism.

Introduction

Human health is laid from the moment of conception in the womb. Further, at the initial stage of life after birth, it is formed in the family; then it is strengthened and supported in pre-school, educational, out-of-school, higher educational institutions; in the process of adulthood – it is supported independently (mainly by means of physical culture). Such a paradigm is embedded in the regulatory framework of Ukraine, programs for educational institutions, etc. [4–6]. However, an analysis of the scientific and methodological literature shows that such a model is somewhat ideal. First of all, it is effective only under one condition - a person must consciously actively act in this direction. That is, strengthening and maintaining human health depends on the effectiveness of the process of educating the individual, the formation of her relevant needs and motivations [10].

A large number of studies are devoted to physical education in preschool, general educational and higher educational institutions. The scientific literature discusses ways to solve the problems of reducing the motor activity of children and youth, an increase in the incidence rate, and shortcomings in the educational process [2; 7–10]. However, a small number of publications have been devoted to the study of the organizational and managerial foundations of physical education of children during leisure time, in particular, to the study of the forms of organization of physical education in children's institutions for health and recreation (CIHR). Although, according to the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, CIHR annually visits from 900 thousand to 1,5 million children every summer – this is about 25% of the total number of students [3].

One of our previous studies [1] compared the intensity of

physical education in schools and summer camps. Conclusions were drawn, in children's health and recreation facilities there is a more intensive process of physical education compared to secondary schools and school institutions of health and recreation. Children are more likely to participate in physical education and sports events. It was suggested that this was due to the use of non-standard means and forms of increasing physical activity in the camps, which determined the **purpose of this study** – to clarify the motives and interests of adolescents regarding forms of physical activity in health and recreation facilities.

Material and Methods of the research

During May-July 2019, a sociological study was conducted among adolescents aged 10–15 years in the amount of 836 people. In the process of the survey, a closed-ended questionnaire was used, the question of which was aimed at clarifying the interests of respondents, their motives and attitudes toward sports and fitness activities. The results are summarized in tables 1–3. The sampling error is 2,5% with 95% reliability of the survey results.

Results of the research

The generalized responses of the respondents presented in table. 1, show that the vast majority of adolescents (from 66,7% to 94,1%) believe that their health depends on daily exercise. In their opinion (from 70% to 100%), physical education and sport are the basis of a healthy lifestyle (Table 1). However, it should be noted that on average 20,9% of adolescents have no idea about the benefits of physical culture for the human body, and 14% do not understand the place of physical activity among the components of a healthy lifestyle.

The main motives for doing physical exercises girls indicate the formation of grace and posture – the importance of this motive is growing from 51,9% at the age of 10 years to 68,2% – at the age of 14–15 years.

Among young men, the dominant motive at the age of 10 years is the influence of physical exercise on the formation of will and perseverance (56,7%), however, starting from the age of 11 years gradually (at 11 years old – 40,0%, at 12 years old – 52,9%, at 13 years old – 63,6%) motivation to form masculinity is growing. At the age of 14-15 years, this motive and motivation for the formation of will and perseverance acquire equal values for adolescents (47,4%). These data confirm the data of special psychological and pedagogical literature on the formation of pronounced gender characteristics of girls and boys in adolescence.

Also analysis of the materials presented in table. 1, showed that the interests of adolescents in sports classes also have their own gender characteristics. So, for collective independent studies in their free time, children mainly choose sports games: at 10 years old – 70%, at 11 years old – 50%, at 12 years old – 47,1%, at 13 years old – 36,4%, at 14–15 years – 52,6%. As you can see, interest in sports games gradually fades with age, and resumes at an age older than teens.

Among girls, the most favorite types of motor activity are various games (at the age of 10 years – 51,9%, 11 years old – 41,7%, 12 years old – 46,7%, 13 years old – 40,9%, 14–15 years old – 22,7%), which are not related to sports, and starting from the age of 12 years, there is an interest in sports games (12 years old – 73,3%, 13 years old – 40,9%, 14–15 years old – 36,4%), which also fades away, as in men.

Further analysis of the survey materials showed a similar attitude of adolescents to the choice of independent exercise. So, if at the age of 10 years old girls indicate badminton (29,6%), and guys indicate table tennis (56,7%), then from the age of 11 years old adolescents leave the standard set of sports and fitness camp shift services and choose the category "other sports".

Considering the dynamics, we notice that such girls at the age of 11 years old – 50%, at 12 years old – 33,3%, at 13 years old – 50%, at 14–15 years old – 36,4%; children at 11 years old – 22,7%, at 12 years old – 47,1%, at 13 years old – 45,5%, at 14–15 years old – 47,4%. In addition, in the sample as a whole, up to 20% of adolescents indicate that they do not have physical education and sports interests and do not participate in such events.

So, the interests of adolescents are diverse, and overwhelmingly non-standard. The only type of motor activity that most adolescents (from 68,2% to 93.3%), regardless of age and gender, choose to organize active leisure – there are hiking trips.

The above is confirmed by the analysis of data on the physical education and health-improving activities offered by the teaching staff (Table 2). So, for children, the most favorite measures are sports (from 54,5% to 73,7%), of which the guys who are interesting for themselves usually choose team sports: at 10 years old – 50%, at 11 years old – 40,9%, at 12 years old – 76,5%, at 13 years old – 45,5%, at 14-15 years old – 68,4%.

For girls, their favorite types of physical activity are dance

Table 1
Motives and interests of adolescents at the expense of fitness classes in CIHR

Survey directions	Age, gender of adolescents and the number of respondents (total n=836 people)									
	10		11		12		13		14–15	
	B n=120	G n=108	B n=88	G n=96	B n=68	G n=60	B n=44	G n=88	B n=76	G n=88
Adolescents who believe that physical education is the foundation of a healthy lifestyle	70	88,9	72,7	87,5	94,1	100	90,9	81,8	84,2	90,1
Adolescents who believe that health depends on active daily exercise	80	66,7	59,1	75	94,1	86,7	90,9	77,3	84,2	77,3
<i>The opinion of adolescents for the formation of the body and personality traits under the influence of physical training and sports activities</i>										
• grace and posture	23,3	51,9	13,6	50	11,8	53,5	–	54,5	5,3	68,2
• courage	37,5	7,7	40,9	–	52,9	–	63,6	9,1	47,4	–
• will and perseverance	56,7	37	36,4	41,7	58,8	53,5	36,4	50	47,4	31,8
• ability to communicate with friends	37,5	7,4	4,5	12,5	5,9	20	–	18,2	15,8	–
• nothing is formed	–	7,4	4,5	4,2	–	–	–	–	–	4,5
<i>The interests of adolescents regarding independent physical education and health classes in the camp</i>										
• play table tennis	56,7	11,1	36,4	4,2	29,4	13,3	9	13,6	10,5	27,3
• exercise on the bar	16,7	7,4	4,5	4,2	17,6	–	45,5	–	26,3	–
• run cross	6,7	22,2	22,7	4,2	17,6	13,3	9	–	21,1	4,5
• play badminton	6,7	29,6	22,7	33,3	–	40	9	40,9	10,5	31,8
• engage in another sport	16,7	3,7	22,7	50	47,1	33,3	45,5	50	47,4	36,4
• not involved	13,3	33,3	4,5	20,8	11,8	20	18,2	–	15,8	9,1
<i>Interests of adolescents about collective fitness classes in a camp organized independently</i>										
• play sports	70	18,5	50	29,2	47,1	73,3	36,4	40,9	52,6	36,4
• play other games	10	51,9	22,7	41,7	29,4	46,7	9	40,9	36,8	22,7
• go in for athletics	10	33,3	18,2	16,7	–	13,3	45,5	4,5	–	13,6
• not involved	10	18,5	4,5	20,8	23,5	–	9	22,7	15,8	27,3
Having a desire to go hiking	93,3	85,2	68,2	79,2	76,5	93,3	90,9	72,7	73,7	68,2

Table 2

The attitude of adolescents to physical training and sports activities in the summer camp

Survey directions	Age, gender of adolescents and the number of respondents (total n=836 people)									
	10		11		12		13		14–15	
	B n=120	G n=108	B n=88	G n=96	B n=68	G n=60	B n=44	G n=88	B n=76	G n=88
<i>The most favorite activities in the camps</i>										
• dance	3,3	33,3	4,5	58,3	11,8	53,3		50	5,3	63,6
• sports	73,3	22,2	54,5	16,7	82,4	6,7	54,5	27,3	73,7	9,1
• cultural	6,7	11,1	18,2	8,3	11,8	20	45,5	22,7	21,1	13,6
• contests	16,7	51,9	31,8	20,8	-	46,7	-	31,8	10,5	13,6
<i>The most interesting sports events in the camp</i>										
• team sports (football, mini-volleyball, basketball, etc.)	50	44,4	40,9	29,2	76,5	26,7	45,5	54,5	68,4	54,5
• outdoor games, folk games	16,7	51,9	22,7	50	11,8	26,7	36,4	31,8	26,3	31,8
• relay races	23,3	11,1	36,4	29,2	11,8	60	27,3	40,9	15,8	4,5
• morning gymnastics	3,3	-	4,5	16,7	11,8	13,3	-	-	-	9,1

events (from 33,3% to 63,6%) and contests (from 20,8% to 51,9%), among which the most interesting for them are those associated with mobile and folk games (especially at 10 (51,9%), 11 (50%), 14–15 (31,8%) years) and relay races (especially at 12 (60%) and 13 (40,9%) years) Also for girls 10, 13 and 14–15 years old, sports games remain, respectively 44,4%, 54,5%, 54,5%.

So, from the foregoing, we can conclude that for adolescent boys, regardless of age, in the exercise and sports, the existence of certain rules and boundaries is very important, which affects their interest and motivation. For girls, on the contrary, the existence of rules and boundaries is a factor that reduces the interest in physical exercises. The absence of such, a variety of emotional colors and motor modes, on the contrary, stimulate the creativity of girls, imagination, which leads them to enjoy motor activity.

This also finds confirmation by comparing the attitude of adolescents to the organization of physical education in the camp and school, namely the presence of adolescents' desire to be a physical officer of the detachment and class, and the desire to help the physical education teacher at school and the head of physical education in the camp (Figure 1).

So, the activities of the class and group physical training organizer are always associated with the implementation of all the rules and regulations, according to the guys are more will-

Fig. 1. Average indicators of the correctness of adolescents to participate in the organization of their own physical education

ing to agree to such functions: in school (50,1%) and in the camp (51,6%). Whereas the number of such girls in school is 28,8%, in the squad – 33,2%. At the same time, more girls want to be the physical training organizer of the detachment than the physical training organizer of the class, due to the greater freedom of choice of forms and means of physical education in children's institutions for recreation and recreation. However, it should be noted that with age, interest decreases and at the age of 14–15 years, children who want to be the group's physical training organizer make up 42,1%, class – 31,6%, among girls, 18,2% and 18,2%, respectively (Table 3).

A similar situation has developed regarding the desire of teenagers to help a physical education teacher and the head of the PE camp. So, the number of children assisting assistants in the camp is 58,9%, while in school – 46,1%. The difference is 12,8% (!). Among girls, the difference is less and is 4,3%. However, the total number of female assistants is less and amounts to 39,4% at school, in camps – 43,7%.

In general, the analysis of the materials of Table 3 allows us to conclude that among adolescents, the authority of teachers of physical culture of a school is lower than the authority of the leaders of PE camps. The relatively low authority of these workers among teenage girls. In our opinion, this is due to the standardization of forms of physical education in secondary schools and the personal qualities of teachers, determines the direction of future research.

Conclusions / Discussion

Thus, the materials of a sociological study showed the diversity and non-standard interests of adolescents in physical education and sports and the gender characteristics of their motivation.

For adolescent boys, regardless of age, the existence of certain rules and boundaries in physical exercise and sports is very important, which affects the growth of their interest. However, the rules and limits at the same time is a factor in reducing the motivation to exercise.

The priority place in the formation of interests and motivations

Table 3

Attitude of adolescents to participate in the organization of physical education in the camp and school

Survey directions	Age, gender of adolescents and the number of respondents (total n=836 people)									
	10		11		12		13		14-15	
	B n=120	G n=108	B n=88	G n=96	B n=68	G n=60	B n=44	G n=88	B n=76	G n=88
Those wishing to help the head of the physical culture of the camp	56,7	44,4	45,5	50	70,6	46,7	63,6	45,5	57,9	31,8
Teens helping physical education teacher	46,7	33,3	45,5	33,3	47,1	53,3	54,5	45,5	36,8	31,8
Wishing to be physical training organizer at school	63,3	44,4	45,5	33,3	64,7	20	45,5	18,2	31,6	18,2
Wishing to be a physical training organizer at squad	50	40,7	31,8	37,5	70,6	46,7	63,6	22,7	42,1	18,2

of adolescent girls is taken by creative activities and forms of physical education, changes in motor regimes, combination with other educational forms and directions that lead to girls getting pleasure from physical activity.

Among most adolescents, hiking is equally interesting. Both boys and girls equally want to participate in them, regardless of age.

Prospects for further research. Based on the findings of this study, there is a need to study the motivation and interests of adolescents in motor activity during leisure time during the school year. They also require the development of organizational and managerial technologies that will take into account the interests and motives of adolescents, with the aim of actively involving them in motor activity.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare that no conflict of interest.

Financing sources. This article didn't get the financial support from the state, public or commercial organization.

References

- Bondar, T.S. (2012), "Characterization of the intensity of physical education in the structure of educational and wellness and upbringing processes", *Pedahohika, psykholohiia ta med.-biol. probl. fiz. vykhovannia i sportu*, No. 12, pp. 28-31. (in Ukr.)
- Vaskov, Yu.V. (2013), *Teoretychni i metodychni zasady navchannia fizychnoi kultury uchniv osnovnoi shkoly: avtoref. dys. d-ra ped. nauk* [Theoretical and methodological foundations of physical education teaching of primary school students: Dr. of Sciences thesis abstract], *Nat. ped. them. M.P. Dragomanov, Kyiv*. (in Ukr.)
- State Statistics Committee of Ukraine (2017), Children's Health Improvement in Children's Health and Recreation Institutions in Summer 2017, available at: https://ukrstat.org/uk/druk/publicat/Arhiv_u/15/Arch_ozd_bl.htm. (in Ukr.)
- VRU (2017), Law of Ukraine "On Education", available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2145-19>. (in Ukr.)
- VRU (1994), Law of Ukraine "On Physical Culture and Sports", available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3808-12>. (in Ukr.)
- VRU (2008), Law of Ukraine "On children's health and recreation", available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/375-17>. (in Ukr.)
- Ivanova, L.I. & Omelchuk, O.V. (2018), "Separate issues of optimization of the legal framework for improving the efficiency of physical education of students", *Naukovyi chasopys Natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni M. P. Dragomanova. Seriya 15 : Naukovo-pedahohichni problemy fizychnoi kultury (fizychna kultura i sport)*, Iss. 3K (97), pp. 228-231. (in Ukr.)
- Krutsevich, T. (2012), "On the Effectiveness of the Physical Education System in Secondary Schools of Ukraine", *Sportyvnyi visnyk Prydniprovia*, No. 1, pp. 239-243. (in Russ.)
- Ponomaryova, G.F., Bondar, T.S. & Zolochovsky, V.V. (2013), *Pedahohika fizychnoho vykhovannia: suchasni orhanizatsiini tekhnolohii u zahalnoosvitnikh navchalnykh zakladakh* [Pedagogy of Physical Education: Modern Organizational Technologies in Secondary Schools], Kharkiv. (in Ukr.)
- Sutula, V.O., Bondar, T.S. & Vaskov, Yu.V. (2009), "Formation of physical culture of personality strategic task of physical education of students of secondary schools", *Slobozhans'kij naukovo-sportyvnyj visnyk*, No. 1, pp. 100-105. (in Ukr.)

Received: 19.07.2019.

Published: 31.08.2019.

Information about the Authors

Taras Bondar: PhD (Physical Education and Sport); University of Customs and Finance: 2/4 Volodymyr Vernadsky Street, Dnipro, Dnepropetrovsk Region, 49000, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-1389-6614

E-mail: tsbondar@gmail.com

Iryna Holoviichuk: PhD (Physical Education and Sport); University of Customs and Finance: 2/4 Volodymyr Vernadsky Street, Dnipro, Dnepropetrovsk Region, 49000, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-9259-8203

E-mail: irinaucf@gmail.com